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Abstract

This experiment tested if learning can be enhanced through self-generated coding. A random sample of 72 primary students was assigned to four conditions: control, specific coding, self-generated coding, and dual coding. Recall rates were measured for 20 words. It was hypothesized that self-generated coding would outperform specific coding, and dual coding would yield the highest results. Data were analyzed using a One-Way Analysis of Variance and post-hoc pairwise comparisons. Results showed significant differences among the groups. The first hypothesis was supported; self-generated coding $(M=10.72)$ significantly outperformed specific coding $(M=6.17)$. However, the second hypothesis was rejected. Dual coding was not significantly better than self-generated coding; in fact, self-generated coding performed slightly better. Thus, the study recommends instructing students to prioritize self-generated coding strategies to maximize learning efficiency.

Effect of Elaborative Rehearsal and Imagery on Learning

Aminul Islam^a and Muhammad Kamal Uddin^{b*}

Abstract : The concern of the present experiment was to test whether learning can be enhanced through self-generated coding. A randomly drawn sample of 72 primary students was subjected to four conditions, namely control, specific coding, self-generated coding, and dual coding. We measured the recall rate of each group for 20 words. We expected that the effect of self-generated coding would be significantly better than specific coding on learning. We further expected that the effect of dual coding learning would be significantly higher than both specific and self-generated codings. Data were analyzed through One-Way Analysis of Variance followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison. Results confirmed our hypotheses partially. Overall, results indicated that the groups differ significantly from one another. The first hypothesis had been supported indicating that self-generated coding is significantly better than specific coding. However, the second hypothesis was not accepted indicating that dual coding is not significantly better than self-generated coding. It is a matter of surprise that self-generated coding was slightly better than dual coding condition. Therefore, we can instruct students to emphasize on self-generated coding.

Keywords: learning, coding, control process, specific coding, dual coding

Introduction

Learning is a relatively permanent change in a person's knowledge or behavior due to experience. It depends largely on memory. We can control learning using some control processes, such as elaborative rehearsal, coding, and imagery (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968). Elaborative rehearsal involves repeating information by thinking about the meaning of the information and connecting it to other information one already has stored in his or her long-term memory. Coding attempts to place the information to be remembered in the context of additional easily

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retrievable information, such as a mnemonic phrase or sentence. Coding can be one of two types; specific coding and self-generated coding. Specific coding involves interpretation of an item or event given by the context or experimenter; it's specific because one doesn't have the opportunity to change its meaning. Self-generated coding allows the participants to generate an elaborative meaning to a word as they wish.

Gallimore, Lam, and Speidel (1977) conducted a study on elaboration and overt rehearsal titled as 'The Effects of Elaboration and Rehearsal on Long-Term Retention of Shape Names by Kindergarteners'. In a study with both theoretical and curriculum-development implications, they compared these two control processes to facilitate kindergarteners' retention of shape names. They defined elaboration as the association of two unconnected stimuli (a shape name and a common object). Induced overt rehearsal involves merely repetition of the shape names. A third condition, which held other elements of instruction constant, served as control. The results indicated that superior long-term retention was produced in the elaboration condition. Analysis of short-term data suggested acquisition was complexly affected by experimental conditions. Shepard (1967) showed that recognition accuracy for visual imagery is very high. Subjects in his experiment viewed 612 pictures at a self-paced rate and were later given a recognition memory test on pairs of pictures. Each pair consisted of a picture they had previously seen and a novel picture. When they were tested 2 hours later, the participants were virtually perfect in identifying which member of the pair they had seen.

The main purpose of the present study was to investigate the differential effects of experimenter-instructed and control codings on learning. Then we would compare these results with the effect of dual coding learning. That means we wanted to find out whether provided elaboration, specific coding, of a particular word helps to recall that word better than the elaboration created by the students themselves, self-generated coding. Finally, we also wanted to find out whether dual coding strategy is really the best technique to remember a word as expected by Paivio (Paivio, 1969).

Practically, we were actually trying to provide teachers with more effective learning strategies with a theoretical base at hand, especially for primary students in Bangladesh, where they (strategies) will be more effective. Students may find learning interesting and more effective than ever before. Moreover, we know that school dropout is a significant problem in Bangladesh, especially in the rural areas. We expected that this initiative may decrease the level of school dropout of the students who omit school earlier as they find learning difficult. Ultimately, we may find a more educated Bangladesh

To differentiate our study from the one conducted by Gallimore et al. (1977), it should be noted that they were concerned with pair-associate stimuli. In contrast, we presented students with only a single word by each 5-second interval, and they coded the word as they wished. That means we emphasized totally on self-generated coding. As a result, we can generalize our findings more efficiently. In addition, we wanted to compare these results with the effect of dual coding learning which is a unique addition. If our hypotheses would come out as successful, we would be able to encourage our students to apply the more useful control process to learning, whenever possible, with reference to a better theory at hand.

Methods

Participants

To conduct this study, we purposively selected 72 students from three primary schools. All of them were from either class IV or V. We chose those students with good academic results because we needed those who were fluent in reading and writing. Participants were then randomly assigned to four conditions, 18 in each.

Apparatus

A software which presents a list of 20 common Bengali words for a certain period of time, data collection sheet, paper and pencil were used as apparatus. Stimuli were presented on a computer display in Bengali format.

Procedures

Participants positioned in front of a computer display at a viewing distance of 40 cm. At first, under control condition, participants were presented with a list of 20 words. Each word lasted for a period of 5 seconds, followed by the next word in the list. No special instruction about the control processes was given to this group. They were simply asked to try to retain those words. It would formulate a baseline condition to compare with. The dependent variable of the present experiment was the number of correct response participants could recall out of 20. Slight spelling mistakes had been accepted but notation of a totally new word was not allowed. Spelling mistake was allowed because our intention was to measure learning capacity not intelligence level of individual students. It should also be considered that misspelt words are quite common and acceptable in primary levels. No time limit was determined for recalling words. Participants could recall until they themselves gave up.

It should be noted that throughout all of the conditions, participants had been given a simple mathematical task, which lasted for approximately one minute, immediately after presenting the list. It kept them busy and vanished items from the short-term memory (STM). Then their recall would be retrieved from the long-term memory (LTM) - the items which they really learnt from this task. So, we could be sure of that the items they recalled were the items they really learnt. Participants were allowed to recall items in any order they wished.

Secondly, under specific coding condition, participants were presented with the same 20 words consequently. Participants were given a specific mnemonic code introduced by the experimenters (us) for each word. These are the codes that they were compelled to use to facilitate learning. Thirdly, under self-generated coding condition; participants were given the freedom to use any code they wished to relate to each word, which in turn related the words to the information stored in LTM. Only the words were displayed. Remember, they were not compelled to use a specific code for each word as the previous condition instructed. They were taught carefully how to use various control process to facilitate learning. But they were free to use any method they preferred. Although it seems that instructions for control and self-generated coding are almost the same, we should consider the grade levels of the participants studied. Naturally it can be assumed that students of class IV and V are not able to use highly effective learning strategies on their own. It should be noticed that participants in the self-generated coding are carefully introduced with the effective learning strategies but not for the control one. This is the experimental difference.

Finally, rather than presenting merely with words and their associated codes, participants in the dual coding group were presented with both the words and their associated visual pictures. Thus, they got both the visual codes and semantic codes which might increase the rate of recall. The dependent variable was the number of items that students could recall out of 20 under each condition. This was the measure on the basis of which we would compare the four conditions.

Data analysis

One-way Analysis of Variance was used to analyze the data. It usually provides an overall estimate of all of the conditions concerned. But we also employed a post-hoc test to compare the conditions pair-wise.

Results

We observed from the Table 1 that the lowest score was obtained by specific coding group ($M = 6.17$) and the largest value by self-generated coding group (M

= 10.72). This result apparently supported our first hypothesis which stated that the effect of self-generated coding would be significantly better than specific coding group. The second largest value was for the dual coding group ($M = 9.39$).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for the Four Conditions

Group	N	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE</i>
1	18	8	1.879	.443
2	18	6.17	1.917	.452
3	18	10.72	3.25	.766
4	18	9.39	2.45	.578

Note. 1 = Control Group *M* = Mean Value
 2 = Specific Coding Group *SD* = Standard Deviation
 3 = Self-generated Group *SE* = Standard Error
 4 = Dual Coding Group

Remember our second hypothesis which stated that dual coding group would have a greater recall than self-generated group. Here we apparently observed a contradiction. However, these all were mere observations. These differences could be due to some extraneous variables of which we were not aware, or the differences could be so insignificant for the sample concerned that we could easily neglect them. To be sure of whether the groups really differed significantly from one another we needed to run statistical test on the obtained data. In this regard we preferred one-way ANOVA, and its subsequent post-hoc test. We preferred one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), because we had four groups at hand; we wanted to compare each of them with another (pair-wise) simultaneously.

Table 2 displays $F(3, 68) = 11.505$, which was significant at $p = .000$ level, that, in turn, indicated, overall a highly significant difference among four groups. We concluded from the Table 2 that each of our conditions differed significantly from one another, since $p < .05$. But from this overall estimation alone we could not determine which condition differed from which and how much significant were

Table 2

Overall Comparisons of the Conditions

	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Between Groups	205.264	3	68.421		
Within Groups	404.389	68	5.947	11.505	.000
Total	609.653	71			

they. That's why we proceeded to run a post-hoc test including all of these conditions and scores which provided a pair-wise comparison between groups.

In Table 3 - *a. Control Group versus others*: The first row compared between the control group and the specific coding group. Since $p < .05$, there was a significant difference between these two groups. It should be noted that from the Table 1 we found that the mean for the control group was 8.00, whereas 6.17 for the specific group. Although the difference was significant for these two groups, we favored the control group over the specific one.

Table 3
Post-hoc Test; Pair-wise Comparisons among Groups

Conditions	Mean Difference	SE	p
a. 1 versus 2	1.833*	.813	.027
b. 1 versus 3	-2.722*	.813	.001
c. 1 versus 4	-1.389	.813	.092
d. 2 versus 3	-4.556*	.813	.000
e. 3 versus 4	1.333	.813	.106

Note. * $p < .05$

b. Control group versus Self-generated coding: The second row put the scores of the self-generated coding condition against the baseline. The p-value ($p = .001$) indicated that these groups were highly significant ($p < .05$) in difference from each other.

c. Control versus Dual Coding group: The third row compared the dual coding group with the baseline. With a p-value of .092, it indicated that there was not any difference between these groups.

d. Specific coding versus Self-generated coding: The fourth row of Table 3 directly compared the mean scores of the specific and self-generated coding groups. This was the concern of the first hypothesis which stated that the effect of self-generated coding would be significantly better than specific coding on learning. From the Table we observed that the significance level ($p = .000$) absolutely supported this hypothesis. The mean score for the self-generated group ($M = 10.72$) differed significantly from that of the specific group ($M = 6.17$).

e. Self-generated coding versus Dual coding: Finally, there was a comparison between self-generated and dual coding groups. The significance value, $p = .106$, indicated that there was no significant difference between these two experimental group. It should be noted that it was a clear contradiction of our last hypothesis which stated that the effect of the dual coding learning would be significantly higher

than the other three conditions. From Table 1 we found that the mean value for the self-generated group ($M = 10.72$) was higher than the dual coding group ($M = 9.39$). It proved that students under the self-generated coding condition recalled more items than those in the dual coding group.

Discussion

Learning is a relatively permanent change in a person's knowledge or behavior due to experience. The purpose of the present study was to test whether learning can be enhanced by using some control processes. Drawing 72 elementary level students randomly from the target population, we conducted this experiment under four conditions to determine whether each of these conditions has differential effect on the learning capacity of the students in general. Results of the present study differed somewhat from our hypotheses. Overall, we observed a highly significant difference among four groups. We can conclude that each of our conditions differs significantly from one another. That means each condition contributes to learning differentially. To specify the individual contribution of each condition we ran a post-hoc test. The first comparison was between control and specific codings. Although the difference was significant for these two groups, we favored the control group over the specific one, which was contradictory to hypothesis. In practice, we can conclude that specific coding given for each word during conduction under specific coding condition didn't help students to learn the words on the list. Rather they would do much better without such instruction. When we compared self-generated coding with the baseline, we found that these groups are highly significant in difference. It should be noted that it was our main concern and the self-generated group was our main experimental group. Since the self-generated group differed significantly from the baseline group, we can conclude that whatever treatment we presented for this special group was effective and this special instruction helped them to recall more words than the baseline group which did not have any special instruction.

On the contrary, the comparison of dual coding with the baseline indicated that there was not so difference between these groups. Here we also observed another anomaly of our last hypothesis which stated that dual coding learning was the best of all. However, we saw from the significance value that the dual coding group was only slightly better than the baseline. The comparison between specific and self-generated coding group satisfied our first hypothesis. The mean score for the self-generated group ($M = 10.72$) differed significantly from that of the specific group ($M = 6.17$). In practice, we can say that special instructions given to the self-

generated group about how to make learning more effective did actually help this group to recall more words than other three groups. Students learn more information and thus learning becomes more effective when they learn to make strategies by themselves and think more creatively.

Finally, the last comparison was between self-generated and dual coding group. The significance value indicated that there was actually no significant difference between these two experimental groups. It should be noted that it was a clear contradiction of our last hypothesis which stated that the effect of the dual coding learning would be significantly higher than the other three conditions. We found that the mean value for the self-generated group ($M = 10.72$) was higher than the dual coding group ($M = 9.39$). It proved that students under the self-generated coding condition recalled more items than those in the dual coding group. So, the hypothesis has been reversed in this case. We can explain this finding by arguing that when students make learning strategies from their own experiences independently and more logically, the effectiveness of their learning is enhanced. It can even exceed the findings of dual coding theory (Paivio, 1969), which states that visual imagery is the most effective learning strategy ever proposed.

In conclusion, we can say that self-generated coding is the best of all control processes. When students are motivated to use their own unique talents to code materials, they find learning more effective and more permanent. The next contribution is for the dual coding group. We can further conclude that when students are motivated to apply dual coding techniques organized by them, they will learn best.

Self-generated coding should be more acceptable as the best control process when we skim through the finding of a study conducted by Mei-Liang Amy Kuo and Simon Hooper (2004). They investigated the effects of different approaches to learning Chinese characters. The results indicated that participants who generated their own mnemonics demonstrated higher posttest performance than those in visual coding, verbal coding, and translation groups; subjects in the dual coding group scored higher than those in the translation group.

One limitation of this finding can be ascribed to its generalizability. The sample consisted of students from class IV and V who were collected from three schools in a village. This finding might not be applicable to students studying at upper level. It should be also noted that primary students are naturally noisy and frequently go out of control. Only one research assistant cooperated with me. If we could control environment more strictly, we might find a more accurate and reliable result.

We all know the importance of education in a general way. Education is the backbone of a nation. Here in Bangladesh we also believe it. But the use of effective learning strategy is a matter of concern. Do teachers use the effective strategies appropriate to the different levels of students? If yes, then what is their theoretical base? If not, then it should be ensured. We were actually trying to provide teachers with more effective learning strategies with a theoretical base at hand, especially for primary level students, where they would be more effective. Now we expect that by applying our research findings, students will find learning interesting and more effective than ever before. Moreover, we expect that this will decrease the level of school drop out of the students who omit school earlier as they find learning difficult. Ultimately, we will find a more educated Bangladesh.

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